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Comparative Effects of Collaborative and Individualized Instructional Strategies on Performance in Biology among Undergraduate Students in Benue State University, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of collaborative instructional strategy (CIS) and individualized instructional strategy (IIS) on students' performance in biology education in Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental design was used for the study. Two research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of all the biology education students in Department of Science and Mathematics Education during the 2024/2025 Academic Session, Benue State University, Makurdi with 80 students as sample using Stratified random sampling technique. Biology Education Students Performance Test (BESPT) with 50 items constructed by the researcher which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.80 and validated by an expert in Science Education was used to collect data for the study. The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the independent sample t-test was used to test the research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed among others that the students taught Biology Education using CIS have higher

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academic performance than those taught using IIS, The *t*-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of students taught Biology Education courses using CIS and those taught using IIS recorded *t*-test value of 0.055 with a *p*-value of 0.02. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.02<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Both the male and female students have higher academic performance when taught with CIS, The *t*-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using CIS and those taught using IIS recorded *t*-test value of 0.055 with a *p*-value of 0.040. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.040<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The study recommended among others that the National Universities Commission, Ministry of Education and all stake holders should ensure that University lecturers especially in biology education should vary their instructional strategies to include Collaborative Instructional Strategies.

Keywords: Biology, Education, collaborative, individualized, instructional Strategies.

Introduction

The 21st century has revolutionized teaching and learning in all subjects with assorted innovative strategies. This development has changed the forms and mode of education drastically in both developed and developing countries. According to Ferlazzo (2015) there are many strategies now that teachers can use to motivate learners and ensure that knowledge is fully impacted. In most countries of the world now, teaching and learning is mostly done through the aid of innovative strategies such as; collaborative, jigsaw, individualized strategy, cooperative instructional strategy among others (Angura & Abakpa 2018). These strategies gives learners the opportunity to actively engaged with a task which they accept is for learning, that means learners are not simply following a prescription or set of rules, but contribute their own thinking to the task through hands on activities making learners the owners of knowledge (Ünal, 2017). In Nigeria just like any other country in the world; teachers and lecturers are poised to vary their instructional methods especially in activity oriented subjects like Biology at all levels of education. The current Nigerian Secondary School Biology Curriculum is developed to provide students with the knowledge of the concept in Biology to ensure that students learn biological concepts meaningfully to promote their understanding of the world around them. This can

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only be achieved if students are actively exposed to innovative learning strategies in Biology.

Adam, Lameed, Ayodele, and Muraina (2023) states that Biology is a key science subject designed to produce individuals, some of whom may or may take biological studies in their professional pursuits. It is however hoped that in whatever profession they finally find themselves, the biology education they acquired in school would be of value to the totality of their education. Biology is a popular science subject taught at the Senior Secondary School level. One primary function of Biology teaching is to help the students understand biology concept, principles, theories and laws. Ahmad and Sari (2019) opine that the Biology Curriculum in Nigeria aims at developing broadly applicable skills, such as: problem solving, communication, critical thinking and objective reasoning abilities to enable students prepare for work place and self-sustainability in the world economy. The author explained further that Biology teaching involves exposing the students to several opportunities to understand different types of concepts, principles and help the students have direct contact with the physical materials that will make some meaning to their cognitive framework in the study of science.

According to Ogunleye (1999) Science teaching in Nigeria started during the period of Christian missionaries who introduced western education in Nigeria. This started with the establishment of Church Missionary Society (CMS) grammar school in Lagos, Nigeria in 1859. Others include the Roman Catholic Missionary (RCM), African Mission of South Baptist Convention, Wesleyan Methodist Mission, among the rest of United Presbyterian Church of Scotland Mission, and the Qua Ibo Mission. The foundations of science education were created and injected into schools' curriculum. The subjects include arithmetic, algebra, geometry and physiology. Other schools established by the missionaries are grammar schools, teacher training schools, pastoral schools, vocational schools, agricultural schools and the introduction of elementary science in the school curricular and the students are being taught. The curriculum contents are reading, writing, arithmetic and religion. Before the year 1931, only very few students in secondary schools tried science at external examinations conducted by Oxford and Cambridge examination board and those students that tried it, failed.

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The pressure from Nigerian nationals who had the opportunity to study abroad and the legislation on education led the colonial government to establish post-secondary institutions, and this marked the beginning of modern teaching of science in Nigerian secondary schools. At that time some rudiments of science education, including "General Science" and "Nature Study," were introduced into the curriculum of schools established by Christian missionaries, but these were not specifically biology. The Biology curriculum was first introduced in 1977. The new Biology curriculum was first published by the Federal Ministry of Education in 1985. The biology curriculum was approved by the Joint Consultative Committee (JCC) on Education in July 1985 and the National Council on Education (NCE) in September 1985.

Biology as a course of study in Nigerian universities emerged with the establishment of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka in 1960, with the Faculty of Biological Sciences created in stages, starting as a Division of Biological Science within the Faculty of Sciences in 1966/67 and later upgraded to the Faculty of Biological Sciences in 1973/74. Biology is offered in almost all public universities in Nigeria, including Benue State University Makurdi where Biology is offered in the faculty of science as B.Sc. and in the faculty of Education as BSc.Ed respectively (National University Commission of Nigeria (NUC, 2024). In Nigerian universities, biology education teaching methods are evolving beyond traditional lectures, incorporating interactive approaches like team-based learning, experiments, and virtual field trips, to emphasize the relevance of biology to everyday life and future careers. Thus, because of the importance of this course of study to humanity, it necessary to check how lecturers especially in public universities have embraced the innovative instructional strategies to enhance students' performance in the course.

According to Qureshi, Khaskheli, Qureshi, Raza and Yousufi (2023) the most widely practiced method of instruction at the higher institution of learning is lecture method. Albeit of its popularity, it also faces criticism by many researchers stating that it does not help in deep understanding of concepts. Modern researchers indicate that if proper and suitable methods and techniques are used, even the student of less intelligence can easily learn. This has resulted in more emphasis on teaching through

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diverse methods and innovative strategies in order to improve learning and understanding. One of these is Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS), which presumes that team effort of students towards single goal of learning a particular aspect result in more understanding than solo efforts (Oyarole, 2016). This method, although have many essential features for improving teaching- learning process, however, is not practiced normally due to many reasons including time and energy required to manage it activities. On the other hand, Ferhat and Mehmet (2016) assert that, students' performance especially in core science can be enhanced if Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) is used where students are exposed to the content and learning techniques and allowed to learn individually instead of team or collaborative work. The author argued that individualized instructional strategy is devoid of distractions thereby encouraging individual students to learn faster.

Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) on a broader scope can be referred to as a teaching strategy that involves students learning together as a team in order to understand and learn content of the subject (Sada & Adamu, 2023). Ishag (2015) opine that collaborative instructional strategy is competence oriented in terms of augmenting academic achievement has been proved by many research studies. The authors maintained that Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) learning also improves positive attitude towards learning, improved social relations, in addition to high self-esteem and cohesiveness, it also improves motivation, class participation and achievement of students. Collaborative instructional strategy is a teaching-learning strategy that actively involves the learners in learning from one another while working in groups. Unal (2017) reckons that it establishes a relationship among students, and then taps into that relationship to promote positive interdependence. The author stated that, the students in collaboration constantly negotiate and share ideas in an attempt to achieve certain learning objectives.

According to Ferreira (2021) CIS is an important in team learning because it create an environment where students are actively involved in the teaching-learning process, and possess four broad attributes: knowledge sharing (the teacher building upon the already existing knowledge the students possess about the course content), sharing ability (teacher encourages students to use what they know, share among themselves and correct each other), mediation (the teacher mediates and directs

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learning) and heterogeneity (students are grouped heterogeneously, with their diverse backgrounds, experiences and perspectives contributing to a more meaningful collaboration. Collaborative instructional strategy facilitates learning because working as a group creates better understanding than doing so individually, students get to voluntarily take part in discussions and there is more opportunity for the student to learn more (Ishaq, 2015).

Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) strategy on the other hand, according to Udo and Onwioduokit (2022), is a teaching strategy which presumes that the students are mentally, emotionally, socially and physically stable and better positioned to learn alone when all the needed materials are provided. It basically serves as an umbrella for a variety of approaches in education that involve joint intellectual efforts of students and teachers. Olayonu and Ojo (2025) states that the students who participate in Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) learning and educational activities outside the classroom get better grades. The authors emphasized that it prepares college graduates to possess the ability to work without depending on anybody to developed suitable skills.

Olatoye, Aderogba and Aanu (2017) stated that in Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) learning strategy, all students are allowed to stay separately and learn. Every student is assigned an objective and the achievement of that objective demands that the students work individually. The Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) learning strategy is student-centered and dominated. In Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) learning settings, learners do not assist one another study and learn task material or the subject matter (Olayonu and Ojo, 2025). Achievement is the action of accomplishing an academic task successfully. Its purpose is to find the stand of a student at a given moment. It has to do with testing the knowledge acquired by the student which help the teacher and the student to evaluate and predict the degree of learning attained. It is useful in testing the retention of information and skill. It is also determinant of the efficacy and efficiency of a given instruction (Ferhat & Mehmet, 2016).

Many scholars have investigated the efficacy of collaborative instructional strategies and individualized instructional strategy particularly at the lower levels of education;

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Sada and Adamu (2023) investigated the effect of Collaborative Teaching Strategy on Academic performance and Retention among Senior Secondary school students in Dutsinma Education Zonal Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. The study was guided by four objectives among which is, 'to Determine the difference between academic performance of Biology students taught using Collaborative teaching strategy and those taught using chalk/talk method. It was discovered that collaborative teaching strategies have a more significant effect on students' performance in biology than the traditional chalk/talk method. Iji, Ochu, Adikwu, and Atamonokhai (2017) examined the effect of collaborative instructional strategy on male and female students' performance in secondary school chemistry in Benue State, Nigeria. Ishaq (2015) determined the effects of collaborative learning strategy on performance among low ability junior secondary school basic science students in Kano, Nigeria. Oyarole, (2016) investigated the Impact of collaborative strategy on retention and performance in ecology concepts among concrete and formal reasoning ability students in Zaria Nigeria. Williams and Akpan (2017) examined Collaborative versus contextual learning and students' academic performance in biology. All the studies reported positive impact of collaborative instructional strategy on students' performance although all at secondary school level.

On the other hand, Dominic, Asogwu and Idomo (2018) examined the global individualized learning strategies adopted by students at University of Nigeria Nsuka in their effort to key into the global education. The main purpose of the study was to determine the level of awareness and utilization of the strategies among the university students. The test of hypothesis revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of the responses of male and female on the level of utilization of individualized learning strategies in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Similarly, Udo, and Onwioduokit (2022) determined the Collaborative, Individualized Learning Strategies and Students' Academic Achievement and Retention in Physics Using the Concept of Waves Motion in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Six research questions and six hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Quasi experimental non-randomized pretest-posttest research design was adopted for the study. Findings of the study indicated that there was a significant difference in academic achievement of Physics students taught the concept of wave motion using

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collaborative learning strategy and individualized learning strategy, in favour of collaborative learning group.

It is not an overstatement that many studies have been conducted in different settings of education, using different kinds of Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) learning innovative strategies or techniques and Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) Such techniques are Learning Together (LT), Jigsaw grouping, Teams-Game-Tournaments (TGT), Group Investigation (GI), Students' Team Achievement Division (STAD), and Team Accelerated Instruction (TAI), Individualized Learning Model, Individualized Assessment Technique among others. Yilshik, Ezekiel and Umar (2020) assert that collaborative and individualized strategies have been reported to be more effective to the demands of high rates of cognitive and affective outcomes more than lecture-based teaching or chalk and talk teaching method. The authors stated that these approaches have been reported to improve students' achievement and knowledge retention. However, most of these studies are carried out in secondary schools and other lower levels of education with only a few conducted using university students. It is on this note that the present study seek to find out if collaborative and individualized instructional strategies have any comparative effect on the academic performance of Biology Education students at Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

The teaching and learning of Biology particularly at tertiary level of education is faced with various challenges that hinder the achievement of the course objective. Some of these challenges include; teachers or lecturers not employing innovative teaching strategies, limited resources like inadequate laboratory equipment, inadequate qualify personnel i.e lecturers/laboratory technicians and assistants, overemphasis on theoretical learning, limited career guidance, societal bias toward non science discipline, examination-focus education system, limited exposure to practical application of Biology among others (Oyovwi, 2022). As a result of these challenges, researchers such as; Ndayambaje, Bikorimana and Nsanganwimana (2021), Ezekiel, Yilshik & Joseph (2021) have continued to report students' poor achievement/performance in Biology due to the above reasons and the fact that the

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teaching methods used the by most of the teachers in the delivery of Biology instruction is lecture method.

This implies that, teaching methods used by Biology teachers during instruction have great effect on the students understanding and mastery of the subject matter and performance generally. Therefore, the problem of this study is that: Do Collaborative and Individualized Instructional Strategies have any Comparative Effects on Students Performance in Biology Education? Hence scholars such as; Ezekiel,(2017), Yilshik, Ezekiel, and Umar (2020) reported that in a typical Biology classroom setting, if students are involved in only passive learning, it would lead to limited knowledge retention and performance, let alone engaging them in critical thinking or promoting functional understanding. Although there are various contributions from scholars yearly to improve students achievement or performance in Biology but search have shown that there is limited work on collaborative and individualized instructional strategies on students' performance in Biology. Therefore, this research seeks to explore the two strategies, particularly the comparative effect on students' performance in Biology.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine whether Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) and Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) have any comparative effect on students' performance in Biology Education in Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Find out the comparative effect of Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) and Individualised Instructional Strategy (IIS) on Students Performance in Biology Education.
2. Determine the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology Education.

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Research Questions

From the objectives of the study, the following research questions guided the study:

1. Is there any comparative effect of CIS and IIS on students' performance in Biology Education?
2. What is the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology?

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁. There is no significance difference on the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on students' performance in Biology Education.

H₀₂. There is no significance difference on the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology.

Methodology

The study determined the comparative effect of Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) and Individualised Instructional Strategy (IIS) on students' academic performance in Biology Education in Public Universities in Nigeria: A case study of Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design was used. The population for this study consisted of all the 100 to 400 levels B.Sc.Ed Biology students during the 2024/2025 academic session in the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University Makurdi. Two levels made up of the sample within the area. The levels were randomly assigned to either the treatment group or the control group. A total of 80 students, 40 from the experimental group and 40 from the control group were selected and participated in the study. The experimental group I and control group II. The experimental group were taught Biology courses using CIS in line with lessons procedure prepared by the researcher while the group II were taught the same Biology courses using the IIS lesson plans. Biology Education Students Performance Test (BESPT) was used to collect data. The 50 items test was based on the course synopsis of 200 and 300 levels Biology Education core courses. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Science Education and one in Test and Measurement. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha and internal consistency of instruments was obtained as 0.80. The data collected was analyzed using mean and

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standard deviation while the two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Independent t-test.

Presentation of Results

The presentation of data for this study is done according to the research questions and research hypotheses.

Research Question 1. Is there any comparative effect of CIS and IIS on students' performance in Biology Education?

Table 1. Mean Performance Score of Students Taught Biology Education Courses using CIS and those Taught using IIS

Group	N	Pre-mean	SD	Post-Mean	SD	Mean Gain
Experimental	40	30.50	3.21	50.53	3.11	19.10
Control	40	23.32	2.30	31.43	2.22	08.11
Total	80					
Mean		7.18		19.01		10.99
Difference						

Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) Scores of Students Performance in Biology Education Source: Field Report SPSS March, 2025.

Table 1 Shows students taught Biology Education Courses using Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS) had BSSPT mean scores of 30.50 and 50.53 with standard deviation of 3.21 and 3.11 respectively. The students taught using Individual Instructional Strategy (IIS) had pre BSTSPT and post BESPT mean scores of 23.32 and 31.43 with SD of 2.30 and 2.22 respectively. The summary of the performance scores shows 19.10 mean gain for the experimental group and 08.11 mean gain for the control group with a mean difference of 10.99 which clearly indicated that the achievement of those in experimental group was higher.

Research Question 2. What is the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology?

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Table 2. Mean Performance Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Biology Education Courses using CIS and those Taught using IIS.

Gender	Method	N	Post-Test Mean	SD
Male	CIS	20	25.22	3.90
	IIS	26	20.18	2.76
Female	CIS	20	27.21	2.70
	IIS	26	18.23	2.56

Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) Scores of Male and Female Students Performance in Biology Education. Source: Field Report SPSS March, 2025.

Table 2 Shows that both male and female students taught Biology Education using Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS) had posttest mean scores of 25.22 and those taught using Individual Instructional Strategy (IIS) posttest mean scores of 20.18 with SD of 3.90 and 2.76 respectively. While the female students taught Biology Education using CIS had posttest mean scores of 27.21 and those taught using IIS had posttest mean scores of 18.23 with SD of 2.70 and 2.56 respectively. This implies that both the male and female students perform higher or better in CIS.

Ho₁. There is no significance difference on the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on students' performance in Biology Education.

Table 4. t-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of students taught Biology Education using CIS and those taught using IIS.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	P	Dec
CIS	40	19.2440	0.5423	0.055	78	0.02	N
IIS	40	08.1722	0.5332				

The t-test of independent sample on the on the mean performance scores of students taught Biology Education using cooperative Instructional Strategy and those taught using individual Instructional Strategy recorded t-test value of 0.055 with a p-value of 0.02. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.02 < 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means there is significant difference on performance

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scores of students taught Basic Science using cooperative group work and those taught using individual study.

H₀₂. There is no significance difference on the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology.

Table 5. t-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Biology Education using cooperative instructional strategy and those taught using individualized instructional strategy.

Gender	Method	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	P	DEC
Male	CIS	20	10.0000	0.5423	0.055	78	0.04	R
	IIS	20	03.1000	0.5332				
Female	CIS	20	09.2440	0.5311				
	IIS	20	05.0722	0.5200				

The t-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Biology education using cooperative instructional strategy and those taught using individual instructional strategy recorded t-test value of 0.055 with a p-value of 0.040. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.040<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means irrespective of sex the students perform higher in CIS.

Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the comparative effect of Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS) and Individual Instructional Strategy (IIS) on academic performance of Biology Education in the Science and Mathematics Education Department, Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria.

It was established that the students taught Basic science using CIS have higher academic performance than those taught using IIS. Thus, the result shows that students taught Biology Education courses using Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS) had BESPT mean scores of 30.50 and 50.53 with standard deviation of 3.21 and 3.11 respectively. The students taught using Individual Instructional Strategy (IIS) had pre BSSPT and post BSSPT mean scores of 23.32 and 31.43 with SD of 2.30

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and 2.22 respectively. The summary of the performance scores shows 19.10 mean gain for the experimental group and 08.11 mean gain for the control group with a mean difference of 10.99 which clearly indicated that the performance of those in experimental group was higher. The t-test of independent sample on the on the mean performance scores of students taught Biology education courses using CIS and those taught using IIS recorded t-test value of 0.055 with a p-value of 0.02. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.02<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means there is significant difference on performance scores of students taught Biology education courses using CIS and those taught using IIS. The result is in agreement with Udo, and Onwioduokit (2022) who reported that students have higher academic performance when exposed to collaborative teaching and learning strategies.

It was revealed that male and female students taught Biology education courses using CIS had posttest mean scores of 25.22 and those taught using IIS, posttest mean scores of 20.18 with SD of 3.90 and 2.76 respectively. While the female students taught Biology education courses using CIS had posttest mean scores of 27.21 and those taught using IIS had posttest mean scores of 18.23 with SD of 2.70 and 2.56 respectively. This implies that both the male and female students perform higher or better in CIS. The t-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using CIS and those taught using IIS recorded t-test value of 0.055 with a p-value of 0.040. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.040<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means irrespective of sex the students achieve higher in CIS. The result is in consonant with Hidayah, Dasna & Budiasih, (2021) who confirmed that cooperative learning strategy have higher students' performance irrespective of gender and school status.

Conclusion

It is concluded that; the students taught basic science using CIS have higher academic performance than those taught using IIS. Both the male and female students have higher academic performance when taught with CIS. Thus for Biology education to be well taught in all in Nigerian Universities, there is need for government and all the stakeholders in science education to motivate and encourage lecturers to always use using innovative strategies particularly Cooperative

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Instructional Strategy (CIS), In order to boost biology education teaching and learning especially at the university level.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made; the government through the Ministry of Education and National University Commission should ensure that:

1. The students at university level are taught Biology education using Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS).
2. Both the male and female students at all levels of Biology education are taught using CIS.

References

- Adam, U. A., Lameed, S. N., Ayodele, B. B., & Muraina, I. O. (2023). Beyond the Confines of Achievement in Secondary School Biology: Higher-order thinking in Focus. *Journal of Educational Sciences*, 7(1), 12-26.
- Ahmad, F., & Sari, N. I. (2019). Improvement of Biology Learning Results Through the Application of Problem-Based Instruction Approach Oriented Think Pair Share Learning Model. *Journal of Applied Science, Engineering, Technology, and Education*, 1(1), 88-93.
- Angura M.T & Abakpa V.O (2018) Impact of Cooperative Instructional Strategies and Conventional Teaching Methods on Students Achievement and Interest in Upper Basic Education Science and Technology in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative research and Development* 7 (2) 23- 35 www.ijird.com
- Dominic T. U. & Asogwa L. (2022) Global Individualised Learning Strategies: A Study of University of Nigeria Nsukka. *Journal of Economics and Environmental Education*. Volume 3, (2) 20-35
- Ezekiel D. P. Yilshik O. M. & Joseph M (2021). Biology Students' Questioning Behaviour in Relation to Their Achievement in Biology in Barkin Ladi, Local Government Area, Plateau State. *Kashere Journal of Education* 2021, 2(2): 71-

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78. ISSN: 2756-6021 (print) 2756-6013 Google Scholar: Retrieved 31st March, 2025.

Ezekiel, D. P. (2017). An investigation into Biology students' questions types in relation to their Achievement in Biology in Barkin Ladi Local Government Area, Plateau State. *Unpublished Master's thesis. Department of Science and Technology Education, University of Jos, Nigeria.*

Ferhat & Mehmet (2016) The Effect of Individualized Instruction System on the Academic Achievement Scores of Students. *Hindawi Publishing Corporation Education Research International Volume 2 (7) 2016, ArticleID7392125, 9pages* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2016/7392125>

Ferlazzo, L. (2015). Strategies for helping students motivate themselves. Retrieved October 6, 2016, from <http://www.edutopia.org/blog/strategies-helpingstudentsmotivate-themselves-larry-ferlazzo>

Ferreira J.M. (2021) "What if we look at the body? An embodied perspective of collaborative learning," *Educational Psychology Review, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 1455-1473, 2021*

Iji, C. O., Ochu, A. O., Adikwu, O. & Atamonokhai, S. E. (2017). Effect of collaborative instructional strategy on male and female students' performance in secondary school chemistry in Benue State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Chemistry 3(6): 94-98. doi: 10.11648/j.ijpc.20170306.15*

Ishaq, U. (2015). Effects of collaborative learning strategy on performance among low ability junior secondary school basic science students in Kano, Nigeria. A Masters Dissertation Report. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University.

National Universities Commission (NUC) of Nigeria: List of public universities in Nigeria; <https://www.nuc.edu.ng/nigerian-universities/state-university/>

Ndayambaje J.B. Bikorimana E. & Nsanganwimana F. (2021) Factors contributing to the students' poor performance in biology subject: A case study of ordinary level in rural secondary schools of Rwamagana district. *GSC Journal of Biological and pharmaceutical Sciences. ArticleDOI: https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2021.15.3.0163. Google Scholar: Retrieved 31st March, 2025*

(*Comparative Effects of Collaborative and Individualized Instructional Strategy ... Oyak... Et..al. 2025*)

Ogunleye, A. O. (1999). *Science education in Nigeria*. Lagos: Sunshine International Publications Nigeria Limited.

Olatoye, R. A., Aderogba, A. A. & Aanu, E. M. (2017). Effects of cooperative and individualized teaching methods on senior secondary school students' achievement in organic chemistry. *The Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*, 12(2), 310 – 319 24)

Olayonu O.O & Ojo A.E (2025) Effect of Individualized Learning Strategy on Pupils' Academic Performance in Social Studies in Ilorin West Local Government of Kwara State. *International Journal of social Science Humanity and Management research*

Oyarole, A. Y. (2016). Impact of collaborative strategy on retention and performance in ecology concepts among concrete and formal reasoning ability students, Zaria Nigeria. A Masters Dissertation. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University.

Oyovwi E.O. (2022) Biology Education in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges in the 21st Century. t: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361934056> Google scholar. Retrieved 31st March, 2025

Qureshi M.A., Khaskheli A., Qureshi J. A., Raza S. A.& Yousufi S. Q. (2023)“Factors affecting students’ learning performance through collaborative learning and engagement,” *Interactive Learning Environments*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 2371-2391, 2023.

Sada M.U. & Adamu S.O. (2023) Effect of Collaborative Instructional Strategy on Academic Performance and Retention Among Senior Secondary School Students in Dutsinma Education Zonal Quality Assurance. *International Journal of Research in Education Humanities and Commerce Volume 04, Issue 04 "July - August 2023"*.

Schuitema, J., Peetsma, T., & van der Veen, I. (2016). Longitudinal relations between perceived autonomy and social support from teachers, and students’ self-regulated learning and achievement. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 49, 32-45. doi:10.1016/j.lindif.2016.05.006

Udo T.O and Onwioduokit M. (2022) Collaborative , Individualised Learning Strategies on Students Achievement and Retention in Physics in Uyo Local

(Comparative Effects of Collaborative and Individualized Instructional Strategy ... Oyak... Et..al. 2025)

Government Area Using the Concept of Wave Motion. *International Journal of Innovations in Educational Methods* Volume 10, Number 2, 2022. ISSN: 2276-6103 Copyright© Pan-African Book Company 2024 Online Publication: www.irdionline.org in the Pan-African Journal Seri

Ünal, M.2017. Preferences of Teaching Methods and Techniques in Mathematics with Reasons. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*5 (2): 194-202.

Williams, C. & Akpan, K. P. (2017). Collaborative versus contextual learning and students' academic performance in biology. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 7(6), 06-10. DOI: 10.9790/7388-0706070610

Yilshik, O. M., Ezekiel, D. P. & Umar, S. A. (2020). Relationship between secondary school students' selfconcept and academic achievement in Biology in Plateau state central Senatorial zone, Nigeria. *Journal of Science, Technology, Mathematic and Education*, 16(2), 176-185.